

Export of Handicrafts during the Mughal period

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Abstract:

During the advent of Mughal administration, the region of Kashmir emerged as a renowned hub for the manufacture of handicrafts. The Mughal authorities actively facilitated commercial routes, created bridges, and established serais, so significantly fostering the export of handicrafts inside the Mughal suba of Kashmir. The handicrafts were sent too many regions inside India as well as to adjacent nations. South India also evolved as a significant hub for marketing Kashmir handicrafts, leading to substantial income for the region of Kashmir. This study examines the methods by which Kashmir handicrafts were exported. For example, it is worth exploring the trade channels utilized for exporting these handicrafts, as well as understanding the reasons for the widespread popularity of Kashmiri handicrafts among individuals from all regions of India and neighboring countries. Additionally, it is important to assess the extent to which the export of these handicrafts has contributed to the economic and cultural development of Kashmir.

Keywords: Kashmir, Mughal, Trade, Handicrafts, Routes, Market

Introduction:

Kashmir is renowned in medieval literary sources for its picturesque landscapes and the inhabitants for their intellectual acumen and exceptional artistic prowess. The individual was endowed by nature with a plentiful supply of natural resources, which he skillfully transformed into luxurious items that showcased his sophisticated artistic sensibilities, harmoniously complementing the surrounding landscapes. The region of Kashmir has demonstrated a longstanding presence of artistic skills dating back to prehistoric times. Kashmiris are renowned for their intellectual acumen and are often regarded as possessing greater intelligence compared to individuals from other regions of India.¹

Following the advent of Mughal administration, the region of Kashmir emerged as a prominent hub for the manufacture of handicrafts. The acquisition of Kashmir by the Mughal Empire resulted in the widespread recognition and renown of Kashmiri craftsmen on a global scale. The Mughal monarchs effectively managed the commercial routes, overseeing the construction of bridges and serais to accommodate travelers. This strategic approach significantly facilitated the export of handicrafts inside the Mughal suba of Kashmir.²The handicrafts originating from Kashmir were disseminated across various regions of India and even extended beyond its borders via established trade routes. Abul Fazl asserts that the region of Kashmir was interconnected with the external world by a network of 26 trade routes. Among these routes,³ the ones that held significant importance were:

The Muzaffarabad Pakhli Route serves as a vital link connecting the region of Kashmir with Rawalpindi, and subsequently with Peshawar. The

pathway was located at a relatively low elevation, allowing for year-round accessibility.⁴

The Mughal Route served as a vital link between the regions of Kashmir and Punjab. The route traverses the Pir Panjal Pass, specifically in Hastivanj.⁵The closure of this route during the winter months is attributed to its traversal at an exceptionally elevated height.⁶

The Punch Route serves as a connection between the regions of Kashmir and Punch, traversing through the Haji Pir pass. Furthermore, Punch is linked to Jammu through the towns of Rajouri, Thana, Dharamsala, and Akhnoor.⁷ Regarding the Kishtawar route, no information was provided. There exist two distinct pathways that connect the region of Kashmir to Kishtawar. There are two routes to reach Islamabad, also known as modern Anantnag. One route passes through Singhpora,⁸ while the other route travels via Dasu.⁹ The region of Kishtawar is linked to Badarwah and Jammu via the town of Ramban. The Central Asian Trade Route traverses the entirety of Ladakh, spanning from its eastern to western regions. The aforementioned path was deemed traversable solely during the summer season;¹⁰ but, due to its significant economic significance, merchants frequently choose to utilize it even during this period. The region of Kashmir was geographically linked to Central Tibet, Kashgarh, and China. This route facilitated the trade of Kashmir with Bhutan, Nepal, and Bengal.¹¹ According to Abul Fazl, the roads of Bhimber and Pakhli were deemed the most favorable among all available options, as they were typically passable by horseback¹². The handicrafts of Kashmir were exported to Central Asia, Russia, Bhutan, Nepal, Bengal, and Patna via these trade routes.¹³ Over time, there was an expansion of trading relations that reached as far as Bijapur and Golconda.¹⁴The handicrafts of Kashmir that were

produced for commercial purposes encompassed various significant items, such as the Kashmiri shawl, carpet, silk, paper, paper-mache, and carved wooden goods. Out of all the items mentioned, the shawl held the utmost significance and was distributed to many regions inside India as well as its adjacent nations. The textile industry experienced significant growth prior to the Mughal period, but it achieved a higher level of refinement during this era as a result of the adoption of innovative techniques. Consequently, Kashmir gained international recognition for producing shawls that were renowned for their softness, warmth, and delicate texture. During the Mughal era, the city of Srinagar witnessed the operation of an extensive number of looms, exceeding 24,000, dedicated to the manufacturing of shawls.¹⁵

After the completion of the manufacturing process, the shawls were subsequently sent to the wafarosh, an individual who had provided financial support, as well as to the mokhim or broker. These two factors determine the pricing and impact the transaction with the retailer.¹⁶ According to Bernier (year), the shawl business in Kashmir can be regarded as a distinctive feature of the region. The region of Kashmir is known for its significant accumulation of wealth.¹⁷ The Kashmiri shawls were widely utilized by the upper classes and aristocracy in India and other regions. Kashmiri shawls were historically employed as a symbol of opulence and extravagance.¹⁸ the acquisition of a shawl had become a popular trend among the nobility, as it was widely regarded as a status symbol.¹⁹

The Mughal era resulted in an increased commercialization of the shawl industry.²⁰ the loom underwent enhancements, resulting in the introduction of new color variations and the production of shawls in diverse dimensions²¹. The Mughal emperors acquired shawls in significant quantities, both through purchase and as gifts from the Subedars of Kashmir.²² The shawls were additionally dispatched to foreign kings as a gesture of reverence.²³ During the reign of Shahjahan, a significant quantity of shawls were dispatched to the monarchs of Bijapur, Golconda, Rome, Egypt, and Iran.²⁴ The Mughal rulers, particularly Emperor Akbar, not only established extensive wardrobes and storage facilities for the preservation of various items, but also enforced the mandatory use of specific garments by courtiers and officials. These garments included the Takauchiya (a coat), peshwaz (a coat open in the front), and parm-narm.²⁵ (the Kashmiri shawl). According to Abul Fazl, this measure was implemented in order to effectively manage and enhance the demand for various commodities, which received significant attention from Akbar. The Kashmir shawl was extensively utilized throughout the reigns of Jahangir and

Shahjahan as well. The Tuzuk has a minimum of twenty references documenting the bestowal of Kashmir shawls onto individuals of noble status, courtiers, fakirs, foreign envoys, and other individuals as a gesture of favor.²⁶ As a result, Shahjahan had a notable affinity for shawls, both in his own consumption and in his generous distribution of them to the monarchs of Bijapur, Golconda, Rome, Egypt, and Iran.²⁷ Moreover, Shahjahan had a substantial requirement for a multitude of shawls and carpets to furnish the newly erected palaces²⁸. During the reign of Aurangzeb, the manufacturing of shawls in Kashmir reached its zenith and was thereafter sold to many regions around the globe.²⁹ The commercial interest of the East India Company in Kashmiri shawls experienced significant growth starting in 1665, ultimately leading to its dominance in the European market.³⁰ In addition to Lahore³¹, Agra³², Ahmedabad,³³ and Gujarat,³⁴ South India has also evolved as a prominent marketing center for Kashmiri shawls.³⁵ Nepal, Lhasa, and Kathmandu were significant importers of Kashmiri shawls,³⁶ acquiring substantial amounts of these textiles. In a manner akin to shawls, the carpets originating from Kashmir held significant value as a commodity for exportation throughout the Mughal era. The carpets originating from Kashmir were often regarded as being of higher quality compared to the imported carpets from Persia.³⁷ during the Mughal era, the region of Kashmir was known for its production of rugs, namdas, and pile carpets. These goods were carried to South India, where the Deccan kings created a favorable market for them. The woollen carpets that are being preserved in the shrine of Asar Mahal in Bijapur are said to have been acquired by Muhammad Adil Shah from Kashmir in the year 1657.³⁸ It is highly likely that these carpets are part of the collection that has been conserved within the Gol Gumbaz Museum in Bijapur. Based on technical tests, it is highly probable that the objects in question were created in Kashmiri handicraft Karkhanas.³⁹ In the seventeenth century, the hair of the holy prophet in Hazratbal Srinagar was transported from the temple of Bijapur. This implies that the Hamdani/Kubarwiya order established affiliations with the carpet and textile industry, as well as with the veneration of the sacred hairs of the prophet, which were housed in the Asar Mahal in Bijapur and in Hazratbal Srinagar.⁴⁰

The region of Kashmir is renowned for its flourishing silk industry. The silk industry of Kashmir has been highly acclaimed by Mirza Haider Daughlat, Abul Fazl, and Jahangir.⁴¹ Mirza Haider Daughlat considered it to be among the marvels of the Kashmir region.⁴² According to Bernier's account in his Travels, it is reported that certain goods were exported to Lahore.⁴³

The paper produced in the region of Kashmir was highly sought after within India due to its suitability for writing purposes. The object possessed a smooth and lustrous surface.⁴⁴ The paper was sufficiently treated to ensure that, upon washing, all ink residue would be completely eradicated, so allowing for its reuse in writing applications.⁴⁵ The manuscript paper was highly sought after in India and was utilized by individuals seeking to enhance the formality and prestige of their written communication.⁴⁶ According to George Forster's account in his work titled "Travels," it is stated that the Kashmirians were known for their production of high-quality writing paper, which was formerly a highly sought-after commodity in the Eastern region. Significant volumes of paper were exported from Ahmedabad to Persia, with the assumption that the paper originated from Kashmir. In addition, the region of Kashmir was renowned for its production of exquisite woodwork products, which were widely traded across the Indian subcontinent. In his Travels, Bernier made an observation regarding the Kashmiri people, stating that they exhibit a notable level of activity and industriousness⁴⁷. The craftsmanship and aesthetic appeal of their palekys, bedsteads, trunks, inkstands, boxes, spoons, and other assorted items are notably amazing. These objects, produced by their skilled artisans, are widely utilized throughout various regions of the Indies. The individuals in question possess a profound comprehension of the craft of varnishing and exhibit exceptional proficiency in replicating the intricate patterns seen in a certain type of wood. They achieve this by skillfully incorporating meticulously crafted gold threads, resulting in an exquisite and flawless imitation that I have yet to witness surpassed in terms of elegance and precision. The merchants held a significant position in Kashmir society⁴⁸ because to their riches, influence, and power, making them crucial actors in the handicraft trade. Through engaging in trade and commerce, they established political affiliations with distant territories, so assuming a crucial position in the socio-economic and political landscape of Kashmir.⁴⁹ These traders facilitated the establishment of novel marketplaces in distant locations, hence enhancing India's commercial connections with other nations such as Rome, Persia, Egypt, Central Asia, and Nepal.⁵¹ Due to substantial profits, the merchants engaged in year-round journey through several mountains to procure pashm and other raw materials, thereafter selling the produced items.⁵²

Conclusion

During the period of Mughal governance in Kashmir, the handicraft sector exhibited a high level of organization, resulting in the large-scale production of handicrafts. These goods were not

only intended for local consumption, but were also exported to various regions within India as well as neighboring nations. According to Bernier, the utilization of child labor in craft manufacturing was prevalent, resulting in significant economic prosperity. The merchants specializing in handicrafts established marketing centers across various regions in India, Central Tibet, Nepal, and Bhutan. Transactions in these areas were predominantly conducted using a financial instrument known as Hundis. Frequently, the clientele provided recommendations regarding their preferred shawl patterns and designs. The significant demand for Kashmiri handicrafts can be attributed to the extensive number of local and international dignitaries who received them as gifts, as well as the consumption from prominent marketing centers. The procurement and production of handicraft products were overseen by a designated official known as Khan-i-Saman, who ensured timely acquisition of existing items and the manufacturing of new ones.

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